

MESOSCALE MODELLING OF THE WEATHER ABOVE TITAN'S LAKES

Audrey CHATAIN^{1,2,3}, Scot RAFKIN¹, Alejandro SOTO¹, Enora MOISAN^{1,4} and Ricardo HUESO²

© Mark A. Garlick / markgarlick.com

Project funded by the E.U.
Horizon 2020 research program

The map of Titan

© NASA-ESA/Cassini-Huygens

Map of Titan's surface at near-infrared and infrared wavelengths (Seignovert et al. 2019)

Methane hydrological cycle

Methane clouds

Evidence of rain

Turtle et al (2011)

Lakes and seas: an important source of methane vapor

6 seas/lakes between 1200 and 200 km
45 lakes between 200 and 30 km

© NASA

Lakes:

- How much methane evaporates?
- What regulation from the local atmospheric circulation?

Creation of the mtWRF model

Research Paper

Air-sea interactions on titan: Lake evaporation, atmospheric circulation, and cloud formation

Scot C.R. Rafkin^{*}, Alejandro Soto

Icarus 2020

Addition of the solar and infrared fluxes

Chatain et al, PSJ, 2022

Addition of the solar and infrared fluxes

⇒ diurnal variation of the lake breeze

Moving to 3D!

Sea breeze from lake to land at the surface

Subsidence over the cold lake

Effect of divergence: 2D vs 3D

3D

3D equivalent of 2D simulations

Strong effect of divergence on winds

⇒ sea breeze less extended over land in 3D (by divergence effect)

⇒ subsidence over the lake stronger in 3D (by convergence effect)

Effect of shoreline

⇒ Surface wind: adapted to the lake shape (note: wind stronger over inlets)

Effect of shoreline

⇒ From the surface to ~500 m: local intensification of wind over peninsulas

⇒ Small updrafts over inlet extremities

Interactions between lakes

⇒ Vary with the insolation

⇒ Day: several small lake breeze cells + local wind acceleration

⇒ Night: one large lake breeze cell, hosting internal winds oriented both towards and from the central lake.

Stronger winds with bigger lakes

⇒ Surface winds up to 0.1 m/s over the biggest lakes:
not enough to form waves (require > 0.4 m/s, Hayes et al. 2013)
(except maybe during storms or with a specific topography of the shoreline)

Higher humidity at the surface with bigger lakes

⇒ Reaching 95% humidity in the northern section of Jingpo lake
(and more is expected as lands are for now 100% dry and flat in the model)
⇒ (Could maybe form fog?)

Adding the topography around lakes

Adding the topography around lakes

⇒ High ramparts deform the lake breeze but do not stop it!

Effect of land surface properties on the lake breeze?

Small lakes surrounded by terrains with different surface properties (roughness, emissivity, albedo, thermal inertia)

=> see the poster by Enora Moisan #26

Small effect on air-sea interaction

⇒ slightly more evaporation in 3D

⇒ but a bit less methane vapor accumulation over the lake in 3D (due to winds)

⇒ lake slightly colder in 3D

New effect with background wind in 3D

Background wind from GCM (collab. J. Lora)

⇒ Formation of a pocket of accelerated wind behind the lake (not seen in 2D)

